

Review

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Delayed Anthropocene in the deep-sea biosphere: a last paradise soon lost?

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The deep sea remains a last paradise and the place of minimal human impacts compared with other ecosystems. However, this pristine status is rapidly changing, and deep-sea human impacts have seldom been discussed in a broad context that draws comparisons with those in other ecosystems. Here, we recap the history of human-induced ecological degradation in deep-sea, shallow-marine and terrestrial ecosystems to place the deep-sea situation in a broad context. Anthropogenic terrestrial ecosystem degradation started tens of thousands of years ago. Shallow-marine ecosystem change followed that of terrestrial degradation but also began several millennia ago. More substantial degradation commenced from the time of civilization, European colonization and industrialization. However, deep-sea ecological degradation started much later. In the deep sea, most major human impacts began much later than the industrial revolution, e.g. deep-sea trawling from the 1950s. Major near-future concerns include deep seabed mining and marine carbon dioxide removal. Deep-sea Anthropocene biosphere degradation is delayed in this regard, and the ecological integrity of the deep sea remains much better than in other ‘paradises’ such as tropical rain forests and coral reefs that are already degraded substantially. The deep sea could soon be similarly degraded if large-scale implementation of mining and/or marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) technologies commences.

This article is part of the theme issue ‘The biosphere in the Anthropocene’.

1. Introduction

Human activities have transformed Earth’s biosphere over tens of thousands of years [1–3], but such transformation accelerated exponentially after industrialization and into the Anthropocene [4,5]. Acknowledging ongoing debates on the timing of the Anthropocene [6], here we use Anthropocene to indicate the general periods of substantial human influence; we do not use it as a chronostratigraphically defined epoch with a precise global start date [7]. The timing of human-induced ecosystem degradation varies among geographical regions [8,9]. Timing also differs among different systems such as terrestrial and marine realms, and even within realms. For example,

shallow-marine (defined here as 0–200 m depth) and deep-sea ecosystems (defined here as > 200 m depth) differ in exposure and response to human activities. But most studies to date have focused on a single system [10–13] with few comparative studies.

Deep-sea ecosystems are not immune to climatic change and direct anthropogenic changes [13–16], a concern increasingly emphasized in recent studies [17–20]. However, many human-induced impacts have only recently extended into the deep sea [13,15,21,22]. Few studies have contextualized the status of deep-sea ecosystems regarding human-induced impacts compared with other ecosystems, especially from an historical perspective. Here, we summarize the history of human-induced impacts in deep-sea ecosystems and compare that history with those of terrestrial and shallow-marine ecosystems. This comparison clearly indicates delayed arrival of the Anthropocene signature in the deep sea compared with terrestrial and shallow-marine ecosystems and highlights rapid impacts and high risks of near-future acceleration of human impacts in Earth's last ecological paradise, especially if projected large-scale implementation of deep-seabed mining and certain marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) activities proceeds.

2. Pre-Anthropocene human impacts on Earth's biosphere

Numerous studies clearly identify the root causes of substantial human impacts on terrestrial ecosystems, including many pre-industrial effects such as overhunting, farming and deforestation [4,10]. Following the appearance of *Homo sapiens* at approximately 300 000 years ago [23,24] and especially after the out-of-Africa exodus of *H. sapiens* approximately 50 000–120 000 years ago [25–27], human hunting initiated the decrease in large prey in the terrestrial realm from approximately 60 000 years ago [8,28] (figures 1 and 2). At the time of the last deglaciation, overhunting had already led to a collapse and mass extinction of large mammals by approximately 15 000–12 000 years ago [8,27,33,34] (figures 1 and 2). Human-induced deforestation and land modification gradually became substantial during the middle Holocene [4,10] (figure 1).

Major human impacts on shallow-marine ecosystems emerged later than those on terrestrial ecosystems (figure 2). Although archaeological evidence of marine exploitation dates back to over 100 000 years ago [35], small human population size and simple hunting and fishing tools led to relatively local impacts on marine ecosystems at that time [35]. More major overexploitation and early eutrophication impacts in marine environments began hundreds and even thousands of years ago [9,11,12,30,35–39] (figure 2). For example, four vertebrae from a sperm whale (*Physeter macrocephalus*), including one with an embedded bronze spearhead, attest to the seafaring skills of the Phoenicians who occupied the Eastern Mediterranean from approximately 1550 to 300 BCE and suggest that they may have been among the first to hunt large cetaceans [40]. Aristotle (384–322 BCE) reported the disappearance of bivalves such as scallops from the Bay of Kalloni as a result of intensive fishing [41]. In San Francisco Bay, white sturgeon abundance and size decreased from 2600 to 700 years ago through overexploitation [35,42]. Overexploitation of sea otters in the Northern Pacific kelp forests began approximately 2500 years ago [11,43]. The extensive deforestation carried out by the ancient Romans from approximately 0 to 500 CE caused severe soil erosion and the release of sediments that altered coastal underwater landscapes in the Mediterranean basin [44]. The Romans also strongly promoted the introduction of alien species. For example, the Roman emperor Tiberius (42 BCE–37 CE) imported thousands of parrotfish (*Sparisoma cretense*) from the Eastern Mediterranean Sea to the Tyrrhenian Sea, an action that undoubtedly altered associated food webs [45]. European settlement and deforestation around Chesapeake Bay, eastern United States, resulted in increased river discharge and initial eutrophication that changed diatom abundance and floral composition around 1700 CE [9,46] (figure 2). In a Norwegian fjord, marine ecological degradation probably started at approximately 1550 CE, associated with initial eutrophication caused by coastal sawmills [9,47,48]. Decline in habitat builders (e.g. corals, seagrasses and oysters) became significant from approximately 1500 to 1800 CE [12,30] (figure 1).

But such early human impacts probably spared the deep sea, and despite these diverse impacts on terrestrial and coastal environments, deep-sea ecosystems probably retained their highly pristine status prior to industrialization.

3. Anthropocene human-induced impacts

Regardless of the exact timing of initiation of the Anthropocene, industrialization quickly accelerated human-induced impacts. Industrialization changed many variables with potential impacts on natural systems, including major issues of chemical synthetic fertiliser, industrialization of fishing, various pollutants and acid rain [10,11,36]. Although major degradation had started in terrestrial systems long before the Anthropocene, industrialized farming, land use change, pollution and other human activities accelerated the degradation of those ecosystems [4,10], with spillover effects on coastal systems. Rapid population increase and massive chemical synthetic fertiliser use affected both terrestrial and shallow-marine ecosystems, causing eutrophication and resulting in coastal deoxygenation [49–52] (figure 2). As the primary cause of marine ecosystem degradation, industrial-scale overexploitation since 1800–1900 CE [11,29,31,53], which was further accelerated by modernization of fishing ships in the late twentieth century [54], quickly paralleled earlier terrestrial overhunting [5] (figures 1 and 2). Pollution impacts in coastal ecosystems date back to the early industrialization period [9,55] with continuing appearance of emergent chemicals/pollutants [56,57]. The timing of the emergence of these major Anthropocene impacts depended on the timing of industrialization [9]. Major impacts had already begun by approximately the 1800s in North America and Europe when their industrialization accelerated, with a much later start in Asia, post-1900 [9].

Figure 1. Historical trends of human-induced impacts on terrestrial (top), shallow-marine (middle) and deep-sea ecosystems (bottom). Percentages of natural and seminatural land are from [4]. Terrestrial megafaunal extinction is from [8]. Shallow-marine biodiversity is from [29] as proportion of non-collapsed taxa. Shallow-marine habitat builders (e.g. corals, seagrass, etc.) decline are from [12,30]. Shallow-marine fishing catch is from [31]. Deep-sea fishing catch from [14,32]. Curves are simplified to illustrate general trends and do not reflect exact data. The red dotted line is our speculation of a possible past–present–future deep-sea biodiversity trajectory.

4. Delayed Anthropocene in the deep sea

Some terrestrial impacts now reach the deep sea, including chemical pollution and debris originating on land. Acknowledging lower pollutant concentrations in deep-sea environments, bioaccumulation has nonetheless led to high concentrations of organic pollutants in the deepest parts of the ocean—the trenches at depths >10 000 m—where concentrations can even exceed those in industrialized shallow waters [58,59]. Between 3 and 11 million tons of macro-plastic reside on the ocean floor, much in the deep sea on continental slopes [60]. Plastics also accumulate and abound in deep trenches [61]. Industrialization has also resulted in novel, direct human impacts on the deep sea. Dumping of sewage, chemical and industrial waste (e.g. from DDT production), radioactive waste and munitions in the deep sea began in the late 1940s [13,15,62] (figure 2). Whereas such activities were typically local in scale and deep-ocean dumping has now been banned, some illegal dumping presumably continues. Industrial deep-sea fishing/trawling also began in the 1950s (figure 2), resulting in rapid overexploitation [32] (figure 1), in tandem with massive seafloor habitat destruction, ghost fishing and extensive bycatch leading to instances of endangered species [14,63,64]. Deep-sea scientific drilling (from the 1960s) has also impacted deep-sea ecosystems [15,65]. Deep-sea oil and gas exploitation began in the 1990s (figure 2), and drilling installations have continued to move into increasingly deeper water, sometimes utilizing seabed pipelines to transport oil and gas [15]. Large-scale oil spills—once limited to land and shallow water—now occur in the deep ocean [66,67]. Communication cables placed in the deep sea in the 1850s, initially for telegraph transmission (in the Mediterranean), now extend to deployment of other types of communication cables throughout the deep ocean floor [68]. In waters where fishing gear impacts can occur, burial of cables may be required (with associated seabed disturbance). Cables may also emit electromagnetic radiation, and we have as yet little information regarding any potential resulting impacts on deep-sea biota.

All of these impacts began later than parallel human impacts on terrestrial and shallow water (figures 1 and 2). For example, commercial large-scale, deep-sea fishing began in the 1950s [15], almost a century later than shallow water, industrial-scale marine fishing [31,69]. Even earlier, the Caribbean Sea ecosystem had collapsed from overfishing of megafauna by European colonizers [11,70,71] along with North Atlantic cod [69] and numerous aspects of coastal ecosystems [12]. But evidence of

Figure 2. Conceptual visualization of historical human-induced impacts on terrestrial, shallow-marine and deep-sea ecosystems and delayed deep-sea Anthropocene. Terrestrial history includes the appearance of *Homo sapiens*, hunting–gathering, post-colonial and post-industrialization developments and impacts. Shallow-marine history includes early and industrialized fishing, eutrophication and pollution, and some other examples (e.g. aquaculture and offshore wind turbines). Deep-sea history includes dumping, fishing, scientific drilling, oil spill, oil and gas exploitation, and future potential mCDR and seabed mining. Anthropogenic warming is indicated as a coloured bar below the terrestrial panel. Examples are to show a visual summary of the delayed deep-sea Anthropocene compared with those in terrestrial and shallow-marine systems, and thus not exhaustive.

the collapse of deep-sea fisheries was first reported for orange roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*) in the 1990s [72]. Despite the relatively recent history of deep-sea fishing, fishing activity in increasingly deeper waters has accelerated rapidly [73]. This activity often leads to rapid depletion of the resource [72] owing to typically slow growth rates, high longevity and low fecundity in deep-sea fishes [72]. Deep-sea fishing catches have generally declined sharply in recent decades, suggesting that overfishing of stocks is taking place [14,32]. In summary, compared with shallow marine fishing, declines in deep-sea fisheries have occurred over a much narrower time frame, although with a similar endpoint of frequent and often severe depletion [31,74,75] (figures 1 and 2).

Marine pollution alters marine organisms in many different ways that span cellular, organismal and ecosystem levels. But in the deep sea, despite well-documented presence of contaminants, few studies to date have addressed obvious harmful impacts, potentially relating to the remoteness of the research area and challenging research logistics of working with deep-sea biota. For example, material from deep-sea dumping can enter into food webs [76], but with unknown ramifications for deep-sea biota. Even for deep-sea oil spills, we have limited knowledge regarding how they affect deep-sea organisms [67].

Warming, acidification and deoxygenation in the deep ocean have occurred over extended periods and are projected to intensify by 2100 [77]. Repeated hydrographic observations, Argo floats, long-term instrument moorings and ocean observatories collectively document climate-induced changes in the deep ocean [77,78]. However, the degree of impact from ongoing climatic change on deep-sea ecosystems remains poorly documented [19,77,78]. Even small changes in temperature can strongly affect deep-sea biodiversity [79,80]. Thus, ongoing warming has probably already affected deep-sea biodiversity as the warming pushes the (often narrow) thermal envelopes that characterize many deep-sea species [80] e.g. as known from the recent invasion of king crabs in the Antarctic deep sea [81], along with effects on population connectivity [82] as well as changing habitat suitability [83]. Nonetheless, undersampling of the deep ocean leaves such impacts on species' distribution, growth rates, reproduction and behaviour largely unknown. Thus, significant uncertainty remains regarding potential delays in anthropogenic warming-induced change in the deep sea compared with shallow-marine ecosystems (figure 2). In shallow-marine ecosystems, the impact of anthropogenic warming was already evident early in the twentieth century [84]. Similarly, deoxygenation and ocean acidification already affect the deep ocean (most severely at bathyal depths), but there are relatively few direct studies of specific impacts [18,19,85]. Insights on potential deep-sea biodiversity loss and extinction risk by warming

and deoxygenation come from the fossil record of, for example, the end-Permian extinction event [86]. In sum, despite clear evidence of deep-sea ecological degradation, the deep sea remains the 'last paradise' on Earth with minimal human-induced impacts relative to most or all of Earth's ecosystems.

5. Deep-sea Anthropocene future: a last paradise soon lost?

Humanity is currently debating additional and very substantial modifications to the deep sea. These activities include deep seabed mining and various forms of mCDR that use the deep ocean as a carbon repository (figure 2). Nations have targeted the Clarion–Clipperton zone (CCZ), a huge deep-sea area at 3500–4500 m depth, for polymetallic nodule mining [17]. These nations aim to extract nodules rich in Co, Ni, Cu and Mn to provide metals to support the green revolution (electric car batteries, solar panels, wind turbines and electronics). Expected impacts include massive seafloor habitat disruption, widespread sediment plumes that can smother animals and clog feeding apparatus, release of toxic compounds and radioactivity, pollution from noise, light and vibration, and more [87], that can cause direct mortality or disturbance to seafloor and water column biota [15,88,89]. Biological research in the CCZ has revealed unexpectedly high, mostly undescribed biodiversity (estimated total species richness in CCZ is >6000 to >8000; and 88–92% of them remain undescribed and unnamed) [90] and very slow recovery rates from disturbance for animals [17] and even microbes [91]. Mining simulation studies from other locations such as the DISCOL (DISturbance and reCOLonization experiment) site in the Peru Basin [92,93] further attest to long recovery times for different groups of biota. Despite a call for a moratorium on deep-seabed mining signed by dozens of countries and many international organizations, the International Seabed Authority has granted mining exploration contracts in international waters to some 21 countries, some of which are actively advancing mining plans [94].

Strategies for mCDR include sinking large biomass (algae, crops, wood waste), iron fertilization, artificial upwelling, ocean alkalinity enhancement, direct ocean capture of CO₂ and deep subsurface CO₂ injection [95–97]. Another climate mitigation strategy proposes bubble enhancement designed to alter ocean albedo. Rapid development of these technologies, often by companies that plan to sell or accumulate carbon credits, has engendered scepticism among some scientists regarding their effectiveness [22,98,99]. Nonetheless, others argue that near-future, large-scale implementation seems possible for some approaches [100–102]. Many of these concepts, for example—iron fertilization or biomass sinking—will affect the deep sea and its ecosystems indirectly through organic matter flux from the ocean surface to the deep sea and lead to oxygen loss [103]. Some others, for example direct deposition of carbon dioxide into the deep subsurface seabed, could affect deep-sea ecosystems directly by causing hypercapnia [22]. Since ongoing human-induced climatic change will affect deep-sea ecosystems negatively through warming, deoxygenation, acidification and changes in organic matter flux [18,19], it is essential to assess the net impact of these mitigation measures [20]. Synergistic effects of mining and climate change also occur [89]. On continental margins and seamounts, deep-sea fishing can further degrade the ecosystem [64]. If this scale of deep-sea disturbance/modification becomes common or accelerates in the future, the deep sea could rapidly lose its status as Earth's last paradise (figures 1 and 2). Avoiding a fate for the deep sea akin to degradation of the Amazonian rain forest, one of Earth's richest ecological systems and the source of many medicines and natural products, will require immediate moratoria for its exploitation and an urgent call for international action to acquire sufficient knowledge of this portion of the global biosphere to enable an ecosystem-based and sustainable management plan [13,104]. But there is hope. The United Nations Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction Agreement [105], a major new international treaty that will enter into force in 2026, has been described as 'the most important ocean agreement to be adopted in more than a quarter century' [106], and it promises protection for biodiversity and sustainable use of deep-sea resources.

6. Challenges and prospects

The fragmented governance of the deep sea creates challenges in addressing anthropogenic change. One hundred and forty nations govern their exclusive economic zones (in 75% of which, by area, the depth is >200 m, i.e. deep sea), whereas multiple sectoral agencies and conventions within the United Nations (UN) govern areas beyond national jurisdiction (96% deep water). Within the single, interconnected global ocean, ocean processes and organisms do not adhere to jurisdictional boundaries, so decisions made to mine, dump or mitigate in one place can affect other jurisdictions. That the anthropogenic changes described above occur remotely and out of sight, in contrast to those on land, adds unique challenges, noting that most countries have little to no access to the deep ocean [107].

In this study, we mostly discussed 'fast-track' anthropogenic deep-sea impacts that cause effects directly, immediately (e.g. fishing, dumping, oil spills) or in weeks or months [108,109] (e.g. iron fertilization changes to surface primary production that sinks to the deep-sea floor as particulate organic carbon flux). But some other impacts could be 'slow-track'. For example, we know little about time periods needed for diffusive processes and bioaccumulation of land-sourced pollutants. Legacy and emergent pollutants have both been detected in deep-sea organisms [110,111], implying relatively short accumulation periods. However, bioaccumulation could have long-term implications because deep-sea organisms are long-lived, with some species living >100 years [112,113]. Slower possible impacts include collapse of the ocean conveyor belt known as the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation as a result of anthropogenic warming [114,115]. Strong evidence shows that changes in deep-water circulation affect deep-sea biodiversity and ecosystems [16,116]. Such impacts could be delayed hundreds to a thousand years depending on the region. For example, deep water formed in the subpolar North Atlantic Ocean needs a thousand years to reach the North Pacific Ocean via the Southern Ocean [117]. Thus, although slow-track anthropogenic deep-sea impacts could be elusive, they are no less important than fast-track impacts.

Ethics. This work did not require ethical approval from a human subject or animal welfare committee.

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Declaration of AI use. We have not used AI-assisted technologies in creating this article.

Authors' contributions. M.Y.: conceptualization, investigation, project administration, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; J.Z.: conceptualization, investigation, visualization, writing—original draft; R.D.: investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; L.A.L.: investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; P.V.R.S.: investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

All authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed therein.

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